

THE ROLE OF INDEPENDENT WORK IN THE CREDIT-MODULE TRAINING SYSTEM

U. T. Usarov¹ , G.Yu. Nodirov²

professor, department of «Social and natural sciences», Samarkand state university of architecture and civil engineering, Samarkand, Uzbekistan¹

teacher, department of «Social and natural sciences», Samarkand state university of architecture and civil engineering, Samarkand, Uzbekistan²

Abstract. *The main task of higher education is to form the creative personality of a specialist capable of self-development, self-education, and innovative activity. Independent work of students plays a key role in the conditions of the credit-module education system (CMSE). The work examines the main aspects of the role of (CMSE) in the training of specialists.*

Key words: *Self-development, self-education, credit-module system, Moodle, Google Classroom.*

Introduction

In order to determine priority areas for systemic reform of higher education, raising the process of training independently thinking highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities to a qualitatively new level, modernizing higher education, development of the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies, the concept of development of the higher education system in the republic was approved. The transition in the republic to a credit-modular education system requires a more responsible attitude towards new pedagogical technologies in the education system. Independent work of students plays a major role in KMSE. The system of independent work of students is focused on the development of competencies, independence and responsibility of students. The paper examines the main aspects of the role of students' independent work in KMSE.

Discussion

In the credit-module system, the emphasis of responsibility for learning shifts from the teacher to the student. Independent work becomes the main tool for achieving educational goals. This encourages students to take a conscious approach to learning, develop time management and self-organization. Flexibility in learning. Independent work allows students to independently choose the pace and volume of studying the material. They can work in depth on those aspects of a subject that are most interesting or challenging to them Development of key competencies. Independent work develops skills such as:

- Analysis and synthesis of information.
- Problem solving and research activities.
- Critical thinking.
- Skills in working with scientific sources and preparing scientific papers.

The role of the teacher as a mentor. In KMSE, the teacher plays the role of a consultant and mentor, guiding the learning process. Instead of presenting the material directly, the teacher provides resources, sets tasks, and corrects students' independent efforts.

Assessment of independent work. Independent work is assessed through a credit system, which makes its effectiveness measurable. An important role is played by:

- Constant monitoring of task completion (tests, controls).
 - Projects and practical assignments.
 - Self-assessment and reflection.

Interaction with modern technologies. KMSO actively uses electronic resources, such as:

- Distance learning platforms (LMS).
- Scientific literature databases.
- Interactive training materials.

Organizing independent work for students requires an integrated approach, which includes planning, motivation, provision of resources and control. Basic steps:

1. Defining goals and objectives. It is necessary to clearly formulate what students need to learn. Divide tasks into clear steps. Relate objectives to real-life examples or professional activities to highlight their significance.

2. Planning and structure. Prepare a study plan that includes clear deadlines. Create step-by-step instructions or checklists for students. Break large tasks into small parts to reduce your stress levels.

3. Providing resources. Prepare educational materials: articles, video lectures, presentations, links to useful resources. Use educational platforms (for example, Moodle, Google Classroom)

for posting assignments and materials. Provide access to libraries, databases or simulations as needed.

4. Motivation: Explain how completing assignments will help them in their studies and professional lives. Encourage the use of independent work to improve skills (critical thinking, analysis, information retrieval). Use gamification elements (points, achievements) or projects that are interesting to students.

5. Control and support. Regularly check the completion of tasks (interim reports, tests, meetings). Organize consultations or discussions to answer questions. Give detailed feedback, highlighting successes and areas for improvement.

6. Use of technology. Introduce interactive formats: online forums, webinars, interactive tests. Use task management software (eg Trello, Notion).

7. Development of independent work skills. Teach students how to plan time (time management). Conduct master classes on searching and analyzing information. Teach them to set goals and record performance results. Regular support and creating a collaborative atmosphere will help students cope with tasks and increase their interest in learning.

Let's consider the difference between students' independent work under the modular-credit system (MCS) and traditional teaching methods in a number of aspects:

1. Organization of the educational process

- ISS: Training is divided into modules, each of which has clearly structured goals, objectives and expected results. Student independent work (SWS) is integrated into each module and is assessed for credits.

- Traditional methods: Independent work is usually less structured, and the volume can be set at the discretion of the teacher, without necessarily linking it to the credit system.

2. The role of the teacher

- MKS: The teacher acts more like a tutor or consultant who guides and coordinates the work of students.

- Traditional methods: The teacher plays a key role in imparting knowledge, and independent work is perceived as a complement to lectures and practices.

3. Scope and planning of CDS

- MKS: Independent work takes up a significant part of the educational process (up to 50% of the time). Specific tasks are developed for it that must be completed to achieve the competencies laid down in the module.

- Traditional methods: The amount of SRS is often determined at the discretion of the teacher or students are expected to allocate their time independently without clear instructions.

4. Assessment

- MKS: Completion of SRS assignments contributes to the final grade for the module. Each module ends with a knowledge test (test, project, report), which encourages students to work systematically.

- Traditional methods: Independent work is assessed less frequently and, as a rule, indirectly (for example, through checking notes, completing homework).

5. Skills and autonomy

- ISS: ISS promotes the development of skills in independent search, analysis and application of information. Students learn to organize their time and work for the long term.

- Traditional methods: Students' independence develops to a lesser extent, since the main focus is on mastering the material provided by the teacher.

6. Use of technology. • MKS: Often involves the active use of educational platforms, electronic resources and interactive forms of work (video lessons, online tests, databases).

- Traditional methods: The use of technology may be less intensive and optional.

7. Target orientation.

- MKS: Independent work is aimed at achieving specific competencies prescribed in the educational program.

- Traditional methods: Focus more on overall learning rather than on specific skills and results.

Thus, within the framework of the modular-credit system, students' independent work becomes more structured, focused and integrated into the educational process, which requires greater responsibility and independence from students.

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